

Additional file 6. Characterization of the *E. faecium* E745 transposon mutant library, showing the number of reads that were mapped to the *E. faecium* E745 chromosome and plasmids. The height of each peak represents the read abundance at a specific insertion site. On the y-axis, the number of mapped reads are shown in log scale.